

Contamination of vacuum environment due to gas emission stimulated by friction

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Abstract

Mechanical elements may produce significant contamination of ultrahigh vacuum due to emission of gases from materials under stress and rubbing. Composition of emitted gases and behavior of gas emission was studied for various materials and surface coatings of interest for vacuum engineering. It is suggested that gases dissolved and occluded in the material bulk (H_2 and Ar) and tribochemical reactions (C_xH_y) are the main sources of gas emission. Frictional heating was discarded as the driving force for gas emission. Mathematical apparatus of specific parameters for characterization of gas emission is proposed.

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1. Introduction

Generally, vacuum environment is implicitly considered being extra clean: in vacuum systems - due to continuous pumping and in the space - due to its immense volume. However, in practice, vacuum environment is very vulnerable for contamination in form of undesirable gases, vapours or debris, especially for systems with large number of mechanical components and sliding and/or rolling contacts.

Contamination of high and ultrahigh vacuum environment is of great concern in different terrestrial clean technologies. In nanoelectronic industry, most of vacuum technological processes require very low airborne molecular contamination (AMC) during the process: allowed partial pressures for oxygen, methane, carbon oxides, etc. should be below $(5-8) \times 10^{-11}$ Pa [1]. Hydrocarbon films of only a few monolayers or just one tenth of a monolayer of adsorbed carbon on the surface of a semiconductor structure may lead to loss of process control, especially for front-end processes [2, 3]. In the future, it is expected that

lithography processing will also be performed under vacuum, so the problem of contamination of vacuum environment will rise even more.

Two components of gas emission from the equipment should be distinguished: (i) gas emission from stationary and free surfaces and (ii) gas emission from the moving parts. Recently, a significant progress has been achieved in controlling and reducing the first of these components due to proper selection of materials, surface treatments, coatings, surface cleaning and outgassing methods. However, almost nothing was done to control the second component, i.e. mechanically stimulated gas emission (MSGE). In addition to AMC, moving parts operating in vacuum may produce significant amount of nanometer size wear debris, which concentration on the semiconductor surfaces is also strictly limited. For instance, for wafers of 300 mm in diameter, the allowable number of particles of 25 nm should not exceed 75,4 [2]. There is also a similar situation for space systems: though gas emission is thoroughly controlled for materials exposed to vacuum, emission from moving parts has not been properly concerned despite of a number of early studies of the phenomenon [4-6].

For new generation of clean vacuum and space mechanisms, advanced lubricants and coatings should be developed. For these materials and coatings not only the tribological performance should be enhanced, but also debris generation and gas emission in vacuum should be tailored and controlled. However, these latter problem are frequently ignored in tribological researches.

Though pressure bursts in a vacuum chamber were frequently observed during opening and closing the valves or mechanical manipulation [7], probably first systematic study of the phenomenon of gas desorption at rubbing surfaces was published by Groszkowski in 1961 [4]. The phenomenon consists in emission of gases from surface and bulk of material during and after application of mechanical. Depending on the type of the mechanical action, which can be tension, compression, shear, rubbing, rolling, indentation, etc., and specific gas emission mechanism, different authors referred to this phenomenon as outgassing stimulated by friction [8], mechanically induced desorption [9], fractoemission [10], tribodesorption [3] and so on.

During last two decades the phenomenon of MSGE was studied for several materials including stainless steel, aluminium, copper, germanium, calcite, alkali halides [8-18] and coatings of amorphous carbon [19-21]. There is a consensus that the sources of MSGE for these materials can be classified in the following list [22, 23]:

- 1) desorption of gas molecules being adsorbed on the material surface from the gas phase;
- 2) emission of gases from the bulk of the material;

3) generation of gases due to mechanodestruction, depolymerisation, tribochemical reactions and other similar mechanochemical processes.

In addition, atoms and atomic clusters of the proper material can be ejected due to the mechanical effect as was observed by Dickinson et al. [17, 18, 24] using mass-spectrometry with submillisecond time resolution.

However, very little is known yet on the characteristics, behaviour, sources and mechanisms of MSGE from various constructional and functional materials used in vacuum engineering. Therefore, this work is aimed at the study of the phenomenon of MSGE for several materials and coatings being of interest for development and maintenance of advanced vacuum mechanisms. On the basis of the experimental findings the possible sources and mechanisms of gas emission are discussed. Finally, a mathematical apparatus of specific quantitative parameters for characterization of MSGE from different materials is developed.

2. Experimental

2.1. Experimental set-up

MSGE was experimentally studied using original ultrahigh vacuum system equipped with a reciprocating pin-on-flat friction cell, which was described in details elsewhere [13, 15]. The experimental system is shown schematically in Fig. 1a. The friction cell was specially designed to reduce, if not completely eliminate, undesired outgassing from supports and bearings of the pin and the sample. For this purpose all bearings were taken away from the vacuum chamber and situated at the atmosphere side (see Fig. 1 b). For applying a normal force, F , a lever with unequal arms was used, while the dead load, G , was applied on the atmosphere side of the lever. The normal load varied between 0.2 N and 0.8 N, sliding velocity was 0.18 m s^{-1} , stroke length was 7 mm and the frequency of reciprocating single strokes was between 1 s^{-1} and 2 s^{-1} . A pivot of the lever with two ball bearings situated at the atmosphere side. Flexible bellows with very low stiffness were used to seal the rods supporting the pin and the lever. A quadrupole mass-spectrometer, QMS, mounted to the experimental chamber was used for analysing the composition of discharged gases. The chamber was pumped out through a calibrated orifice, Or, thus allowing quantitative analysis of gas emission rate. Detailed procedure for gas emission rate measuring can be found in our previous publications [25, 26].

The materials and coatings studied in this work are listed in the table. Bulk materials were cut in sheets of typically $15 \times 15 \text{ mm}^2$, polished and cleaned using deionized water, acetone

and ethanol in ultrasound bath. Coatings were tested without additional cleaning after deposition. Optionally, some metal samples were doped with hydrogen using cathodic polarization in 0.1 N solution of H_2SO_4 with or without promoter of H absorption (4% Te_2O_5). During H-doping the current density was constant 10 mA cm^{-2} , whereas the doping duration varied between 2 and 4 hours. The coatings were provided from other groups and were obtained using thermal evaporation (copper), reactive magnetron sputtering (boron carbonitride, TiN:Ag, tungsten carbide), chemical vapour deposition (a-C:H) and ion cluster source (nanoaggregate copper). All coatings were deposited onto silicon substrates. A pin was an alumina ball, 3 mm in diameter. Silicon substrate and alumina pin were selected due to very low concentration of dissolved and occluded gases. Therefore, contribution from the pin and the substrate to the gas emission yield was avoided.

2.2. Gas composition

Though metals, alloys, synthetic rubbers and hard coatings studied in this work had very different structure, chemical composition, and surface conditions; the composition of emitted gases was not so different for these materials. Hydrogen and methane were the main emitted gases for all studied materials and coatings. Additionally argon, CO, water vapours and organic chemical compounds of low molecular weight were observed in the mass-spectra when coatings or elastomers were rubbed. These findings are consistent with previously reported data [6, 8, 9, 11, 15, 16, 27, 28].

Relative emission intensity of various gases largely depended not only on the type of the material or coating but also on the test conditions, and, in many cases, varied in the course of the test. Therefore quantitative comparison of the emitted gas composition for different materials is a very complex task. In this work we compared the relative composition of emitted gases using a qualitative expert appraisal approach. The results for different bulk materials, coatings and elastomers are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2 shows the composition of the emitted gases from a coating of boron carbonitride as a representative example of MSGE. The mass-spectra shown in this figure were obtained before and during rubbing of the coating in the vacuum chamber. One can observe that during rubbing there were an increase in ion currents with mass numbers 2, 15, 16, 17, and 18, which can be assigned to ions H_2^+ , CH_3^+ , O^+/CH_4^+ , OH^+ , and H_2O^+ . In addition, two new peaks appeared in the mass-spectrum. These peaks at mass numbers 20 and 40 were attributed to argon ions.

Except for stainless steel, for bulk metals the emitted gases included only hydrogen and methane. For stainless steel small amount of CO and water vapours were also detected. For iron, steel and nickel gas emission rate was much higher than for copper, tantalum and titanium. For titanium and tantalum the gas emission rate was very low even after hydrogen doping.

For the coatings obtained using Ar plasma argon was normally observed in the mass-spectra of the emitted gases. Denser and harder coatings (tungsten carbide, TiN:Ag) normally had lower total emission rate and lower contribution from the gases other than H₂ and CH₄. Emission of CO from nanoaggregate copper as well as CO, CO₂ and H₂O from boron carbonitride can be attributed to high porosity of these coatings. For amorphous carbon emission rate for methane was higher than for hydrogen.

Among synthetic elastomers with carbon black filler the gas emission rate was the lowest for saturated nitrile-butadiene elastomer (NBR). Then it increased in the following order: non-saturated NBR, ethylene-propylene-diene and polyurethane. In addition to H₂, CH₄, H₂O and CO, traces of low molecular weight hydrocarbons, mainly of ethane and propane, were detected in the mass-spectra of emitted gases. Similar findings were reported for tetrafluoroethylene [29] and polycarbonate [30].

2.3. Behaviour of MSGE

MSGE had a very complex behaviour on different time scales. The behaviour varied depending on the type of material, gas type and test conditions. When rubbing was carried out under constant conditions, i.e. normal load, sliding velocity and stroke frequency, the slow-variation mode of MSGE behaviour could roughly be classified in two scenarios as shown in Fig. 3. The scenario of Type I (Fig. 3 a) is characterized by sharp increase in the emission rate just at the beginning of rubbing followed by gradual decrease. The emission rate normally stabilized at some nonzero value (graph s). For the Type II scenario (Fig. 3 b), the increase in the gas emission rate was more gradual. Then, after reaching the maximum, it stabilized (s₁) or slowly decreased (s₂). Behaviour of Type I was characteristic for methane emission from metals and coatings, whereas the behaviour of Type II – for hydrogen and argon for most materials and coatings.

Usually, for prolonged rubbing gas emission vanished before rubbing termination as depicted by graphs b in Fig. 3 a and b. This effect was more pronounced for Type I behaviour. However, it also occurred for Type II behaviour under low normal load. In experiments with stainless steel, MSGE of hydrogen during subsequent rubbing was partly restored by heating

the sample at 250 °C during 2 hours between rubbing tests or just storing it for 12 hours in vacuum under room temperature. However, MSGE of methane was not restored by heating. In the case of coatings, evanescence of MSGE during rubbing was usually caused by complete coating's wear-out.

In addition to slow-variation mode, periodic gas emission peaks corresponding to each rubbing cycle and some regular or irregular spikes could be usually observed. Inset in Fig. 3 b shows an example of these features of MSGE. The spikes were more pronounced for the behaviour of Type II and were associated with defects generation on the contact surfaces. These findings are consistent with previously published data on MSGE from steel [9, 31-33], iron [34], aluminium [32, 34], and hard polymers [30, 35]. In case of elastomers, the graphs of MSGE were smooth without any peaks or spikes even under loads exceeding the maximum tensile strength.

The behaviour of gas emission after rubbing termination was also different for two scenarios. For the Type I scenario, the emission rate dropped down almost instantaneously when rubbing stopped. However, for the Type II scenario it decayed slowly. In case of hydrogen desorption from nickel, stainless steel and iron this decay lasted up to twenty minutes after rubbing cessation.

When considering the effect of the rubbing conditions on the gas emission rate, no good correlation between the rate of MSGE and the normal load was found for all tested bulk metals and stainless steel. Figure 4 illustrates this finding for nickel samples. In this figure, the total amount of emitted hydrogen, $N_{st,d}$, is depicted as function of the number of rubbing cycles, N_{fc} , and normal load. This finding was surprising since it was generally believed that gas emission is driven by frictional heating [8, 12, 31, 36], which, in turn, depends on the applied load. Similar results were also obtained for some of the hard coatings, although, in general, the emission behaviour for the coatings was much more complex than for the bulk materials.

Though the effect of sliding velocity could not be studied in this work because of the limitations of the existing experimental set-up, the authors studied the effect of the stroke frequency under constant sliding velocity on the gas emission rate for stainless steel [26]. By variation the stroke frequency, the number of adsorbed molecules between consecutive strokes can be controlled. For lower stroke frequency the number of molecules adsorbed on the contact zone should be higher. However, the emission rate in these experiments did not increase with decreasing the stroke frequency. Therefore, it was concluded that in high vacuum the contribution of adsorption to the total gas emission yield was negligible.

3. Discussion

3.1. Sources of gas emission

Likeness of the gas composition and emission behaviour for diverse materials and coatings studied in this work suggests common gas sources and emission mechanisms. Below, possible sources of gas emission are analyzed following the general gas emission sources listed in Section 1.

1) Adsorbed gases. Our experiments with varying stroke frequency showed that contribution from this source was insignificant. This can be attributed to very low rate of arrival of gas molecules at the surface in high and ultrahigh vacuum. In a first rough approach, one can estimate the time required for completion of a 99% of a monolayer with adsorbed gas molecules using the following expression [37]:

$$t = \frac{A}{p}, \quad (1)$$

where p is the gas pressure, $A = 2 \ln 10 n_m \sqrt{2\pi mkT} / s_0$ is the constant depending on the properties of the surface and the gas: n_m is the density of adsorption centres on the surface, m is the mass of the gas molecule, k is the Boltzmann's constant, T is the gas temperature, and s_0 is the sticking probability of a gas molecule on a free surface. For technical metal surfaces at room temperature the calculated value of A is normally between 2×10^{-4} Pa s and 1×10^{-3} Pa s yielding the time of formation of adsorbed layer larger than 2 s [38, 39]. It should be stressed that the values for A are the lower bound estimation corresponding to simplified Langmuir's model in which desorption of adsorbed molecules was neglected. The real values for t can be even lower than the calculated one due to the effect of desorption, deviation of the real adsorption isotherm from the Langmuir's one and other factors. These findings are consistent with a number of experiments with bulk metals [8, 9, 14, 33] in which desorption of adsorbed phases during rubbing was completely negligible or could be appreciated only during the initial period of rubbing, when the adsorbed layer was near to its equilibrium coverage. However, when material has very large specific area desorption of adsorbed phases can be significant, such in case of CO desorption from nano-aggregate Cu coatings.

2) Emission of gases from the bulk. Emission of gases from the bulk of material usually refers to desorption of dissolved gases, e.g. hydrogen from metals, or to liberation of gases occluded or trapped in the micro- and nanovoids, dislocation cores, grain boundaries and other imperfections as in case of argon emission. MSGE of hydrogen from metals follows a

second-order reaction with the mechanism similar to Langmuir-Hinshelwood one [25]. In this reaction there are several steps: (1) diffusion or transport of dissolved and trapped hydrogen atoms from the bulk to the surface, (2) transition of dissolved H atoms from the bulk onto the surface, (3) association of two H atoms to form a molecule, and, finally, (4) desorption of a hydrogen molecule [25, 26]. Gradual increase and decrease of the H₂ emission rate during rubbing (behaviour scenario of Type II) can be related with slow transport of dissolved H atoms from the bulk to the surface.

3) Tribochemical reaction. Methane and other low-molecular-weight alkanes hardly can be dissolved in metals and hard ceramic coatings [8]. Therefore, emission of C₁-C₃ hydrocarbons might stem from tribochemical reactions on contact surfaces. These reactions have not been thoroughly studied so far. One of the plausible reactions of methane synthesis can involve two reaction precursors: adsorbed methyl group (AMC) and hydrogen atom arriving at the surface from the bulk. Consumption of AMC in these reactions can be responsible for the sharp decay of the emission rate of methane during rubbing as described by the behaviour scenario of Type I.

3.2. Activation mechanisms for MSGE

Though frictional heating was considered for long time as the main activation factor for MSGE, some experimental findings contradicted this hypothesis. These findings include among others lack of correlation between the normal load and gas emission rate; and slow desorption decay after rubbing termination. As a rough estimation, the maximal temperature increase can be found from the approximate model [40]:

$$\Delta T_{\max} \leq \frac{2r\sigma\mu V}{\sqrt{1.273\pi(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)}}, \quad (2)$$

where σ is the hardness of the softer material, μ is friction coefficient, V is the sliding speed, λ is thermal conductivity, r is the radius of the contact zone. The subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the indenter and flat sample, correspondingly. Equation (2) was obtained for circular plastic contact under steady sliding regime. It shows that ΔT_{\max} decreases linearly with the decrease in the radius of the contact zone. Analysis of various combinations of materials including steel, alumina, glass, fluorocarbon polymer, diamond, and other, showed that for the radius of the contact zone of 100 μm and the range of the sliding velocity from 10^{-3} to 10^{-1}ms^{-1} ΔT_{\max} does not exceed 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [3, 41]. These conditions are similar to those used in most of our and others MSGE studies. Such insignificant temperature increase is not sufficient to cause

important gas desorption or diffusion [21]. Moreover, after rubbing cessation the temperature drops down in a fracture of second due to thermal conductivity [40] that contradicts with retarded gas emission. So, thermal mechanism of MSGE activation should be discarded under given experimental conditions.

Řepa et al. [8] proposed specific desorption mechanisms of MSGE consisting in direct transfer of the mechanical momentum from the sliding counterface to gas molecules adsorbed on the contact surface. This mechanism can be partly responsible for desorption of adsorbed molecules and activation of tribochemical reactions, but it does not explain retarded gas emission after rubbing termination.

Another possible driving forces of MSGE could be related with structural activation of material in the mechanically affected zone due to plastic deformation [42], triboemission of charged particles [43, 44] and triboluminescence [45]. Plastic deformation of materials has been demonstrated to be very intensive activation factor for many physical processes and chemical reactions [10, 38, 42, 46, 47]. As for MSGE, plastic deformation can significantly intensify diffusion of dissolved gas atoms to a surface due to dislocation motion [32], generation of stress field with high gradients, creation and annihilation of dangling bonds and defects; removal of oxide films, extension of free surface, and so on. There is a number of experimental findings indicating heavy dependence of MSGE upon plastic deformation, wear, fracture and other kinds of material damage [6, 8, 10, 32]. In case of rubbing, this dependence became evident when the amount of desorbed hydrogen, $N_{st,d}$, shown in Fig. 4 was plotted vs. volume of deformed material in the friction zone, V_w , (Fig. 5). This graph is linear irrespective of the normal load and rubbing duration. This finding corroborates the hypothesis of the dominating role of structural activation of MSGE.

3.3. Quantitative characteristics of MSGE

More than fifty years have passed since the first notion of the phenomenon of MSGE; however, it still remains on the margin of different scientific areas without well-established terminology and quantitative parameters. Presently, the comparison of MSGE for different materials is difficult because of lack the methodological bases and quantitative parameters. Development of specific parameters for characterization MSGE is of crucial importance for further advance in understanding the mechanisms of the phenomenon as well as for transfer of this knowledge to industrial applications.

Being non-spontaneous physico-chemical reaction, MSGE depends on the intensity of stimulation factors. Therefore, for characterization of MSGE some specific quantitative

parameters relating the emission parameters with the intensity of stimulation factors should be introduced. In contrast to other stimulated gas desorption, MSGE does not depend on the energy input, but on the intensity of material deformation in the contact zone and surface area subjected to rubbing. Material deformation is responsible for the emission of dissolved and occluded gas from the material bulk, whereas rubbing of the surface accounts for activation of tribochemical reactions. On the basis of these considerations we propose 10 quantitative parameters listed in Table 2. The parameters are classified into two groups: the rate parameters and the integral ones. The procedure explaining how to determine the rate of MSGE has been published elsewhere [26]. Specific parameters 3 and 4 relate the gas emission rate with the apparent contact area, $A_{fr,a}$, and the total swept area, $A_{fr,s}$, correspondingly. Explication of the geometric parameters is given in Fig. 6 a. The parameter 5 establishes the relationship between the rate of MSGE and the total volume of mechanically affected zone, V_w , whereas the parameter 6 – between the gas emission rate and the volume of the active friction zone¹, $V_{w,az}$. The total amount of emitted gases (parameter 7) can be found by integration of the gas emission rate over the total duration of gas emission, which usually is longer than rubbing duration. Parameters 9 and 10 are analogous to the parameters 4 and 5, correspondingly. The parameters 3-6, 9 and 10 can be determined for total emitted gases or for certain gases. The proposed list of quantitative parameters is not exhaustive and can be extended or shortened on the basis of experimental validation and dominating emission mechanism.

Conclusions

MSGE was experimentally studied for materials and coatings of interest for vacuum engineering. Despite of large difference in chemical composition and structure of the studied materials and coatings, the composition of the emitted gases was not so different and included hydrogen, methane, carbon oxides, water vapours and organic molecules of low molecular weight. For the coatings obtained by magnetron sputtering in argon plasma, argon was also detected in the emitted gases. In high and ultrahigh vacuum gas emission can be attributed mainly to the following sources: (i) gases dissolved and occluded in the material bulk and (ii) gases generated during mechanical action as a result of tribochemical reactions. The emission behaviour can be roughly classified into two scenarios: one with sharp increase just at the

¹ The term first suggested by Kragelsky et al. [31] Kragelskii IV, Lubarsky EM. Friction and Wear in Vacuum. Moscow: Mashinostroenie; 1973.

beginning of friction and another one with gradual increase. The first one can be related with tribochemical reactions as dominating emission source, while the second one can be related with emission of gases from the bulk, which process is accompanied by a rate limiting diffusion step. Both experimental findings and simulation indicated that thermal effect of rubbing cannot be responsible for activation of MSGE under given experimental conditions. On the other hand, there is heavy dependence between the total amount of emitted gases and the volume of deformed or damaged material. This finding indicated that MSGE is activated due structural modification of the material, i.e. plastic deformation, fracture and so on.

On the basis of these findings a mathematical apparatus of specific parameters for quantitative characterization of MSGE from different materials has been developed.

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Figure captions

Fig. 1. a) Scheme of the experimental set-up. TMP – turbomolecular pump, RP- rotary formpump, IG1, IG2 – ionization gauges, QMS – quadrupole mass-spectrometer, Or – orifice in the diaphragm, F – applied normal load. b) Schematic view of the friction cell. The sample is fixed at the longer arm, b , of the lever. The shorter arm, a , is sealed using a flexible bellow. The dead load is applied to the shorter arm situated at the atmosphere side. A pivot of the lever with two ball bearings also situates at atmosphere side.

Fig. 2. Mass-spectra of residual gases in the vacuum system before and during rubbing of the coating of boron carbonitride by alumina pin.

Fig. 3. General scenarios of MSGE rate, $Q_{st,d}$, behaviour. a) Type I: emission rate sharply increases at the beginning of rubbing and decays gradually. b) Type II: emission rate increases and decreases gradually. Plots “e” correspond to the case when MSGE evanesces before rubbing cessation. Inset in graph b) depicts fast variation mode with periodic peaks and bursts.

Fig. 4. Total amount of desorbed hydrogen from electrolytically charged Ni as function of the number of friction cycles under various normal loads F .

Fig. 5. The total amount of desorbed hydrogen from Fig. 2 plotted as function of the volume of deformed material in each test. The volume of deformed material was determined from the analysis of geometry of wear scars using white light confocal microscope.

Fig. 6. a) Schematic drawing of the contact for definition of specific quantitative parameters: 1 – pin, 2 – material under study, F – normal load, V_{sl} – sliding velocity, $A_{fr,a}$ – apparent contact surface area, $A_{fr,s}$ – total swept surface area, L_{fr} – stroke length. b) Schematic drawing for definition of volume parameters: V_w – total volume of mechanically affected zone, $V_{w,az}$ – volume of the active friction zone.

Table 2. Specific quantitative parameters of MSGE

N°	Parameter	Symbol	Equation	Units	
				SI	customary
Rate parameters					
1	Total emission rate	Q	^{a)}	$\text{Pa m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$	mbar l s^{-1}
2	Partial emission rate of gas M	Q_M		$\text{Pa m}^3 \text{l s}^{-1}$	mbar l s^{-1}
3	Specific emission rate per contact area	Q_{AC}	$Q/A_{fr,a}$	Pa m s^{-1}	$\text{mbar l s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$
4	Specific emission rate per swept area	Q_{AS}	$Q/A_{fr,s}$	Pa m s^{-1}	$\text{mbar l s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$
5	Specific emission rate per total mechanically affected volume	Q_{VW}	Q/V_w	Pa s^{-1}	$\text{mbar l s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-3}$
6	Specific emission rate per volume of the active contact zone	Q_{VAZ}	$Q/V_{w,az}$	Pa s^{-1}	$\text{mbar l s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-3}$
Integral parameters					
7	Total amount of emitted gases	N	$\int_{t_i}^{t_f} Q dt$	Pa m^3	mbar l
8	Total amount of emitted gas M	N_M		Pa m^3	mbar l
9	Specific amount of emitted gases per swept area	N_{AS}	$N/A_{fr,s}$	Pa m	mbar l m^{-2}
10	Specific amount of emitted gases per total mechanically affected volume	N_{VW}	N/V_w	Pa	mbar l m^{-3}

^{a)} see [22]

Table 1. Relative composition of emitted gases from different materials

	H ₂	CH ₄	H ₂ O	CO	CO ₂	Ar ¹⁾	Other
Bulk materials	Iron	B	B				
	Nickel	A	B				
	Copper	A ²⁾	C				
	Stainless steel AISI 304	B	B	C ³⁾	C		
	Tantalum	B ⁴⁾	C				
Titanium		C ⁵⁾					
Coatings	Copper	B	B			C	
	Nanoaggregate copper	B	B		A		
	TiN:Ag	A	B				
	Boron carbonitride	A	B	B	B	C	A
	Tungsten carbide	C					
	a-C:H	C	B				B
Elastomers	Ethylene-propylene-diene	C	C	B	C		
	Nitrile-butadiene	B	C	C			C ₂ H ₆
	Saturated nitrile-butadiene	C	traces	traces			C ₂ H ₆ (traces)
	Polyurethane	A	C	B	B	B	C ₂ H ₆ , C ₃ H ₈ (traces)

A – intense; B – moderate; C – weak

¹⁾ Only for coatings obtained using Ar plasma

²⁾ Only for samples doped with hydrogen using promoter

³⁾ From ref. [8]

⁴⁾ Only for cold drawn samples doped with hydrogen

⁵⁾ Only for samples doped with hydrogen and at the initial stage of rubbing

a)

b)

